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**O1 & O2A; Laboratory reports on synthesis, preparation, immobilization
and characterization of photocatalytic materials (D1.1, D1.2, D1.3, D1.4 and
D2.1)**

Project: Solar-assisted photocatalytic degradation of perfluorinated compounds in water
(*SoAPperF*), IPS-2002-02-4780.

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Start: 1/11/2022

End: 31/10/2025

Zagreb, November 2024.

1. Experimental procedure for obtaining photocatalysts and co-catalyst materials

Synthesis of SnS₂-TiO₂

Titanium (IV) n-butoxide (Ti(OCH₂CH₂CH₂CH₃)₄, Across Organics, USA), SnCl₄·5H₂O (98%, Sigma Aldrich, USA), Thioacetamide (C₂H₅NS, Sigma Aldrich, USA), glacial acetic acid (CH₃COOH, Fluka, Germany), C₂H₅OH (96%, Carlo ErbaReagenti, France), pentadecafluorooctanoic acid (PFOA), milli-Q water. All the chemicals used as obtained from the company without any further purification.

Synthesis of SnS₂

In order to synthesize SnS₂, appropriate amounts of SnCl₄·5H₂O (0.2M) and C₂H₅NS (0.4M) were dissolved in a mixed solution of ethanol and glacial acetic acid (95:5) with stirring. After 15 min of stirring, sample solution was transferred into a Teflon-lined autoclave which further placed in an oven at 120°C for 12 h. hereafter, the cooled sample was centrifuged and washed several time with water and ethanol before drying it at 65°C for 16h.

Synthesis of TiO₂

In a 100 mL solution of ethanol and glacial acetic acid (95:5), 5 mL aliquot of Ti(OCH₂CH₂CH₂CH₃)₄ was added under vigorous stirring. The resulting clear solution was transferred to an autoclave and sealed tightly. The autoclave was then kept in an oven and maintained at 180°C for 12 h. The obtained white suspension was subjected to centrifugation and washed thoroughly to remove any impurities. The washed solid was then dried in an oven at 65°C.

Synthesis of SnS₂-TiO₂

To prepare SnS₂-TiO₂ composites, the appropriate amounts of precursors used for the synthesis of SnS₂ and TiO₂ were mixed in a total volume of 100 mL of ethanol and acetic acid in a 19:1 ratio. The mixture was stirred continuously for 15 minutes to ensure homogeneity. The resulting clear solution was transferred into a tightly sealed autoclave, which was then placed in an oven maintained at 180°C for 12 hours. After cooling, the sample was centrifuged to separate the solid material, which was thoroughly washed to remove any impurities. The washed solid was dried in an oven at 65°C, and the resulting yellow material was finely ground using a mortar and pestle.

OTHER SEMICONDUCTING MATERIALS SYNTHETIZED

Preparation of SrTiO₃ and N-SrTiO₃

Chemicals: Strontium hydroxide octahydrate (Sr(OH)₂·8H₂O, Sigma-Aldrich, USA), Sodium hydroxide (NaOH, lachner, Czech Republic), Polyethylene glycol (Sigma Aldrich, USA), Deggusa P-25 (TiO₂), Ethanol (EtOH), Ammonium nitrate (NH₄NO₃), Milli-Q water. All the chemicals used in the study were reagent grade and used as received without additional purification.

Synthesis 1: SrTiO₃ was prepared by a facile solvothermal route. For this 6.60 g of Sr(OH)₂·H₂O were added into water and dissolved at 100 °C with vigorous stirring (Solution A). Meanwhile, a suspension of Deggusa P-25 in ethanol was prepared by stirring it for 20 minutes (solution B). After which, solution B was mixed with solution A followed by the subsequent addition of 20 mL NaOH (5M), 20 mL of polyethylene glycol, and 20 mL of milli-Q water with stirring. The final mixed solution was transferred in an autoclave, sealed and placed in a hot air oven for 24h at 200 C for 24 h. The resulting sample was centrifuged to collect the solid material which was washed several times with water and ethanol and kept for drying at 70 °C.

Synthesis 2: For the synthesis of nitrogen doped SrTiO₃ (N-SrTiO₃) all the conditions were kept similar as used for the synthesis of SrTiO₃, only, NH₄NO₃ was used as nitrogen source.

Preparation of Ag₃PO₄/Cu₂O

Chemicals: Following chemicals were used for the synthesis of Ag₃PO₄/Cu₂O nanocomposite: Copper acetate monohydrate (Cu(CH₃COO)₂×H₂O, Kemika, Zagreb, Croatia), D (+)-glucose anhydrous (C₆H₁₂O₆, Gram-Mol, Zagreb, Croatia), Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB, Vienna, Austria), anhydrous Silver nitrate (AgNO₃, Lachner, Neratovice, Czech Republic), Sodium phosphate dibasic anhydrous (Na₂HPO₄, Fluka, Steinheim, Germany), Hydrochloric acid (HCl, VWR Chemicals, Vienna, Austria), Sodium hydroxide (NaOH, Lachner, Neratovice, Czech, Republic), Milli-Q water.

Synthesis 1: To prepare Cu₂O, Copper acetate monohydrate (Cu(CH₃COO)₂×H₂O) and D-glucose was mixed in 120 mL of water in 1:1 molar ratio. After that 1.093 g of CTAB was added in the mixed solution as a stabilizer. The resulting solution was taken in a Teflon lined stainless steel vessel, sealed tightly and was kept inside an oven for 12 h at 100 °C. The sample was cooled at room temperature and centrifuged at 4000 rpm, the collected solid sample was washed with water and ethanol to remove any unwanted impurities. Then it was dried under the vacuum at 60 °C for 24 h.

Synthesis 2: 2.718 g of anhydrous AgNO₃ was dissolved in 80 mL of water to prepare solution A. Solution B was prepared by dissolving 1.136 g of Na₂HPO₄ in 40 mL of water. Hereafter, solution B was added drop wise into solution A with stirring, yellow colour precipitate was obtained. The stirring was continued for 10 minutes. The pH of precipitated solution was adjusted at 6 by adding HCl or NaOH. After that, the sample was filled in an autoclave and placed in an oven at 120 °C for 6 h. The resulting sample was allowed to cool, centrifuged, washed well with water. The solid yellow slurry was dried at 70°C in an oven.

Synthesis 3: 119.8 mg of as prepared Ag₃PO₄ was dispersed ultrasonically in 120 mL of water for 25 minutes. In the dispersed solution, Cu(CH₃COO)₂×H₂O and D-glucose were added in equimolar ratio (1:1) followed by the addition of CTAB (0.025 M). The sample was continuously stirred for 20 minutes then transferred into a teflon lined autoclave. The tightly sealed autoclave was kept in oven at 100 °C for 12 h. The resulting sample solution was centrifuged and washed with water and ethanol to remove any kind of impurity if present. The collected solid sample was dried in a vacuum oven at 60 °C for 24 h.

Preparation of ZnSe

Chemicals: Zinc nitrate hexahydrate ($\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \times 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Carlo Erba reagents, Italy, France), Sodium selenite (Na_2SeO_3 , Across Organics, Geel, Belgium), Hydrazine hydrate ($\text{N}_2\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, Sigma Aldrich, USA), Hydrochloric acid (HCl , VWR Chemicals, Vienna, Austria), Milli-Q water.

Synthesis: In a 100 mL of 56 mM aqueous NaOH solution 0.832 g of $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \times 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 0.521 g $\text{EDTA}-(2\text{Na}^+)$ were dissolved followed by the addition of 0.4842 g of Na_2SeO_3 . Then 10 mL of $\text{N}_2\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ was added with stirring. The obtained sample solution was transferred in an autoclave and heated at 180°C for 6 h in an oven. The solution was cooled down and 5 mL of 1M HCl was added after that solid sample was collected through centrifugation, washed with water followed by ethanol and dried at 70°C in an oven.

Preparation of CuGaS_2

Chemicals: Cupric chloride (CuCl_2 , Sigma Aldrich, USA), Gallium chloride anhydrous (GaCl_3 , TCI, Tokyo, Japan), Thiourea ($\text{N}_2\text{H}_4\text{CS}$) and Ethylenediamine (EDA) were purchased from thermos Scientific, USA, milli-Q water.

Synthesis: In a typical experiment, 3.23 g of CuCl_2 was dissolved in 120 mL of water, and then excess of thiourea (5.48 g) was mixed to which 15 mL of ethylenediamine was poured and stirred. After 10 minutes of stirring 4.23 g of GaCl_3 was added and stirred vigorously for next 20 minutes. The autoclave was sealed and placed in an oven for 15 h at 150°C . The cooled sample was further centrifuged washed and dried at 70°C .

Preparation of carbon quantum dots (CQDs)

For the synthesis of CQDs 1 g of D-glucose was taken in 120 mL of milli-Q water and filled in an autoclave which was then placed inside an oven for 12 h at a maintained temperature 170°C . The obtained brownish-black sample solution was dialyzed for 5 days through a spectra/por membrane (MWCO: 12-14 kDa) in milli-Q water. The water of dialysis process was changed almost every day. The dialyzed sample was further concentrated by evaporating some water at 70°C for 4 h.

Preparation WO₃ and ZnWO₄

Synthesis: ZnWO₄ photoanodes was prepared by electrodeposition from a 25 mL of 25 mM Zn(NO₃)₂xnH₂O and 25 mM H₂W₂O₁₁. The acidic peroxytungstate precursor was synthesized by dissolving metallic tungsten powder (0.95 g) in 10 mL of 30% hydrogen peroxide in a cold water bath. After complete dissolution, excess peroxide was decomposed using a platinum mesh catalyst. The solution was diluted to 25 mM in a 70 : 30 water:2-propanol mixture. The pH of the starting mixture was approximately 1.9, and the acidity of the final deposition solution was adjusted to pH 1.1 by adding 5% nitric acid solution. ZnWO₄ was electrodeposited onto FTO glass by chronoamperometry method at 0,6 V in a stirred solution. The films were subsequently annealed in air at 500°C for 2 h. WO₃ films were electrodeposited from the same deposition solution as the ZnWO₄ films, without Zn(NO₃) precursor.

Preparation of carbon-nitride based photocatalyst

Sample S3N2 was prepared by dissolving 3.68 mL TiCl₄ in a solution of 60 mL distilled water and 4.95 mL 12 M H₂SO₄. After stirring for one day, 0.3 wt% (relative to the mass of the solution) of hydroxypropyl cellulose was added. After dissolution, 2 molar % of NH₄NO₃ (relative to the amount of TiO₂) was added. The powder was prepared by drying the solution in air to produce xerogels. The xerogels were then thermally treated in a muffle furnace at 600 °C for 1 hour to obtain powdered samples.

g-C₃N₄ nanospheres were synthesized using a solid silica template with cyanamide mediated thermal polymerization method. The overall protocol includes various synthetic steps. The synthesis commenced with production of monodisperse solid silica core nanoparticles, with average diameter of ~370 nm. The silica cores were synthesized using a modified Stöber method with tetraethoxysilane (TEOS) as the precursor. To ethanol (absolute, 74.1 mL) was added water (9 mL) and NH₃ (32%, 4.41 mL). The mixture was stirred for 30 min before TEOS was added (5.6 mL). Once the solid SiO₂ cores were formed, they were coated with another layer of dense silica using a mixture of TEOS (4.46 mL) and n-octadecyltrimethoxysilane (C₁₈TMOS, 2.10 mL) silica precursor solution. The mixture immediately became opaque and was left to settle down for 1 h. It was then centrifuged and the solid was collected and dried on 70 °C overnight. The dried powder was calcined for 6 h on 550 °C in air atmosphere. The

C₁₈TMOS acts as a porogen that is removed completely by calcination, generating a mesoporous silica shell around the solid silica core. The size of solid silica core and thickness of the mesoporous silica shell can be tuned by varying the amount of TEOS and C₁₈TMOS silica precursors in these reaction steps. Next, the resulting monodisperse solid core-mesoporous silica shell nanoparticles (SiO₂@mSiO₂, 3.216 g), were used as templates. They were resuspended in H₂O (20 mL) and loaded with cyanamide (16.082 g) that served as a precursor for carbon nitride. The mixture was put on a vacuum line for 3 h and then on ultrasound at 60 °C for 2 h before calcination at 520 °C (with a ramp rate of 3 °C/min) in a tube furnace (TB) or in a MW sintering asset (FlexiWAVE, Milestone s.r.l.) both under N₂ purging. The samples were additionally etched in 1 M NaOH for 12 h to remove SiO₂ inner core and achieve core-shell structure.

2. Characterization and evaluation of synthesized photocatalyst properties

METHODS

Optoelectronic properties determination

Photoelectrochemical measurements (PEC)

OCP measurements were carried out to assess the light response of the photocatalyst and to quantify the photopotential which reflects the charge accumulation and relaxation dynamics of a photoelectrode coated with photocatalytic material. Several different photoelectrochemical measurements (PEC) were conducted; Open Circuit Potential (OCP), Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) in fixed mode (Mott-Schottky analysis) and scan mode (Nyquist analysis) frequency, as well as Chromoaperometry (CA) and Linear Sweep Voltametry (LSV). All PEC measurements were done using a potentiostat/galvanostat (SP-150, Biologic, France) and a LED light source, corresponding absorption spectra can be find in our previous study. All PEC measurements were performed in 0.5 M solution of sodium sulphate in a three-electrode system, consisting of a platinum counter electrode, calomel reference electrode and working electrode in the form of a fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) glass (1 cm²) coated with the photocatalytic material. The immobilization of the photocatalytic materials on FTO glass in the form of three thin layers was done using spin coating method (KW-4 A spin coater, Chemat Technology, USA) and titania/silica binder which procedure was published in previous paper. LSV measurements were carried out with a scan rate of 20 mV/s under the light illumination and in the dark coonditions. EIS measurements were carried out in the dark conditions (Mott Schottky) where frequency was fixed at 3000 Hz and under the illumination (Nyquist) where the frequency range was scanned from 100 kHz to 100 mHz at OCP and dc potential of 0 V with amplitude of ± 5 mV. CA measurement was done for 300 seconds under continuous UV illumination and constant potential of 0.5 V to evaluate the photocatalytic current response over time.

UV-Visible Diffuse Reflectance Spectroscopy (UV-VIS DRS)

The diffuse reflectance measurements were taken on powdered samples using a UV-Vis spectrometer 2600i (Shimadzu, Japan), equipped with an ISR-2600Plus integrating sphere.

Photoluminescence (PL) spectra

PL analysis was conducted at room temperature using Varian Cary Eclipse fluorescence spectrophotometer (Agilent, USA) with excitation wavelengths between 395 and 430 nm.

Surface, structural and morphology properties determination

The crystal structures of the samples were analyzed by X-ray diffractograms (XRD) acquired by using a RigakuMiniflex 600 (Tokyo, Japan) instrument with a Cu K α target at 40 kV and 10 mA. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) was used to determine the morphology, and elemental composition of the material. The specific surface area and pore size distributions were measured on a Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) analyzer. The surface charge properties of the prepared samples and mean particle size were analyzed by a Zetasizer (Malvern, UK) instrument.

Figure 1. Diffuse reflectance spectra of semiconducting materials: pristine BiVO₄, Ag-BiVO₄, and Ag-Fe-BiVO₄ (A), corresponding plots of transformed Kubelka–Munk function vs. the energy of the light (B), and PL spectra (C)

Photoelectrochemical measurements (PEC)

EIS – dark (Mott-Schottky)

In this research, the EFB at the semiconductor/electrolyte interface were obtained from Mott-Schottky plots taken under dark conditions using Equation 3.2.-1

$$1/C \frac{1}{C^2} = \frac{2}{\varepsilon \varepsilon_0 A^2 e N_D} \left(E - E_{FB} - \frac{k_B T}{e} \right) \quad (3.2.-1)$$

where C and A are the interfacial capacitance and area, ε is the dielectric constant of the semiconductor, ε_0 is the permittivity of free space, N_D is the number of electron donors, E is the applied voltage, k_B is Boltzmann's constant, T the absolute temperature, and e is the electronic charge. Plotting $(1/C^2)$ vs. E should yield a straight line from which E_{FB} can be determined from the intercept on the E axis. The value of N_D could also easily be obtained by knowing ε and A .

Figure 2. Mott-Schottky plot of SnS_2 and $\text{SnS}_2\text{-TiO}_2$ electrodes in 0.5 M Na_2SO_4 .

OPEN CIRCUIT POTENTIAL (OCP) measurements

Table 1. parameters obtained by the OCP technique for the as-prepared materials.

material	Light response (ΔE , mV)	Charge recombination rate (k_r , s^{-1})
TiO ₂ (HT)	54.19*	0.030*
SnS ₂ (HT)	166.33	0.0132
SnS ₂ /TiO ₂	212.56	0.0068

EIS – LIGHT (Nyquist plot)

Figure 3. The Nyquist plots of SnS₂ and SnS₂-TiO₂ coated FTO electrodes in 0.5 M Na₂SO₄, in dark and under light illumination.

Chronoamperometry

Figure 4. Chronoamperometry at 0.5 V (vs RHE) for SnS₂ and SnS₂-TiO₂ coated FTO electrodes in 0.5 M Na₂SO₄.

LINEAR SWEEP POLARISATION

Figure 5. Linear-sweep voltamograms scanned in the area from -0.5 to 1,5 V (vs RHE) for SnS_2 and $\text{SnS}_2\text{-TiO}_2$ coated FTO electrodes in 0.5 M Na_2SO_4 in the dark and under light illumination.

UV-DRS results

Table 3.2.2. Bandgap energies of the tested materials.

material	Bandgap energy (E_g , eV)
TiO ₂ (HT)	3.10*
SnS ₂ (HT)	2.20
SnS ₂ /TiO ₂	2.30

Figure 6. UV-Vis adsorption spectra of SnS₂ and SnS₂-TiO₂.

Figure 7. Tauc plot for SnS₂ and SnS₂-TiO₂.

The SEM results for the SnS₂-TiO₂ sample are shown in Figures below at magnifications of 3 μm and 1 μm, respectively. The images reveal a rough surface with a flake-like morphology, which is beneficial for adsorption due to the increased number of active sites provided by the rough texture[1]. The EDS data presented in Figure 1(c) confirms the presence of all the constituent elements of the SnS₂-TiO₂ composite, namely Sn, S, Ti, and O, as expected. Additionally, the elemental mapping in Figure 1(d) demonstrates a homogeneous distribution of Ti and O over the SnS₂ surface.

Figure 8 (a, b) SEM images of the SnS₂-TiO₂ composite, (c) EDS spectra of the SnS₂-TiO₂, and (d) elemental mapping of the SnS₂-TiO₂

The specific surface areas (SSAs) of the samples were determined using nitrogen (N_2) adsorption-desorption measurements. Figure X presents the N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherms for the SnS_2 - TiO_2 composite. The calculated SSA for the composite is $46\text{ m}^2/\text{g}$, which is higher than that of either the SnS_2 or TiO_2 components individually. This enhancement in surface area is likely attributed to the synergistic interaction between SnS_2 and TiO_2 , leading to a more porous structure and increased surface exposure for the composite material. Hysteresis loop indicates it's a type IV isotherm, which suggests the mesoporous structure of SnS_2 - TiO_2 . Pore size diameter of the composite is in between 2-20 nm as can be seen from the Barrett-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) plot (inserts of figure X).

Figure 9. N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherm and BJH plot (inserts) of SnS_2 - TiO_2

The zeta potential is a key characteristic of particles, influencing both their stability and overall properties. A more pronounced zeta potential, whether positive or negative, typically enhances the stability of particle suspensions due to the electrostatic repulsion between particles carrying the same charge, which prevents aggregation. In the current study, the zeta potential was measured at -45.19 mV. The negative zeta potential value of the SnS₂-TiO₂ composite suggests effective dispersion and stability of the particles in suspension. The average particle size of the composite measured by dynamic light scattering (DLS) techniques is 100 nm (Figure 3b).

Figure 10. Zeta potentials of SnS₂-TiO₂

Results on WO₃ and its combinations

Figure 11. a) XRD patterns and b) UV/Vis reflectance spectra of WO₃ and WO₃/BiVO₄ thin films on FTO substrate.

Figure 12. Tauc plots for the band gap determination of WO_3 .

Table 1. Flat band potential of WO₃ calculated using the Mott-Schottky analysis, band gap energy calculated from UV/Vis reflectance spectra and crystallite size calculated from XRD using Debye-Scherrer equation.

	WO ₃ 10 min.	WO ₃ 20 min
Crystalite size / nm	26.996	33.7634
FBP / V vs. SHE	0,265	0,339
Band gap / eV	2.319	2.535

Electrochemical deposition of WO₃

Electrode 1: WO₃ synthesised during 6 minutes

Electode 2: WO₃ synthesised during 10 minutes

Electrode3: WO₃ synthesised during 20 minutes

Electrode 4: WO₃ synthesised during 30 minutes

Figure 13. Electrochemical deposition of WO₃ at 0,6 V

WO₃ electrode characterisation

a)

b)

Figure 13. Linear polarisation for WO₃ electrode under a) dark and b) light in 0,5 mol dm⁻³ Na₂SO₄, 20 mV s⁻¹.

Figure 15. Chronoamperometry response for WO₃ electrode under a) dark and b) light in 0,5 mol dm⁻³ Na₂SO₄.

Open circuit potential monitoring

Figure 16. Open circuit potential monitoring for WO₃

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy

Figure 17. Nyquist diagram for WO₃ electrode 2 and 3 in 0.5 mol/dm³ otopini Na₂SO₄

Figure 18. Mott-Schottky plots of WO₃ thin films on FTO substrate in 0.5 M Na₂SO₄